

Identification and assessment of datasets resulting from federally funded research: A case study of NIAID-funded projects

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Abstract

Projects funded by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) are generating large, diverse, complex datasets that are stored in an array of disparate repositories. To maximize the benefit of these data and conform with policy changes around federally funded research, there has been increased emphasis on data sharing practices and guidelines. Here, we conducted a deep dive of two data intensive projects to better understand current practices. These efforts identified a total of 105 datasets through a combination of automated methods and manual review. Datasets found in Figshare, a generalist repository provided at no charge for researchers, included the richest metadata directly capturing dataset usage and made up the majority of the datasets identified (68 out of 105). Additionally, most of these datasets were viewed or downloaded at least once, though the details of how these data are used or whether they lead to new projects or additional publications has yet to be evaluated. These findings will inform NIAID's future efforts to monitor compliance with data sharing policies and to demonstrate the value of such policies and more broadly, the value of open data.

Introduction

State of open data

The number of open data mandates from funding organizations and policymakers is growing globally and the publication of open datasets has risen dramatically in the past decade (SPARC, 2022) (Michael Anger, 2022). The 2022 State of Open Data survey, which collects responses from researchers around the world, found that four out of five respondents were supportive of open data being common practice. However, survey respondents also felt they received too little credit for sharing their data (Digital Science, 2022). This dissonance between the best practices for data and the perceived lack of personal recognition for this activity presents a major hurdle when trying to motivate their adoption. For example, data shared in a trusted repository and assigned a DOI is more likely to be persistently, publicly available. Nonetheless we are beginning to see that open data can enhance the impact of research and is a valuable part of research output (Federer, 2022) (Colavizza, 2020). Currently, the responsibility to share data often falls on the researcher. Therefore, it is increasingly important to understand the motivations of the researchers; to demonstrate that researchers can receive credit for sharing their data and reuse of it (Heidi J. Imker, 2021); and show that funders and policymakers are interested and able to monitor compliance with these policies.

Open data and data sharing at NIH

Within the United States, both the National Institutes of Health (NIH) - the world's largest funder of biomedical research - and the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) have issued updated policies in recent years. The NIH's new Data Management and Sharing (DMS) Policy will go into effect January 25, 2023 and will require all NIH-supported research generating data to have a DMS plan "that maximizes appropriate data sharing" and

FAIR data principles (Wilkinson, 2016) and implement this NIH-approved plan in practice. This policy aims to foster data stewardship and enhance the discoverability and reusability of data produced by NIH-funded research and facilitate the citation of these federally funded data. While the NIH encourages use of open domain-specific repositories and knowledgebases where available, they recognize that not all data fit into domain-specific repositories. To fill this gap, the NIH also provides guidance on the use of generalist repositories and is funding the Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (National Institutes of Health, 2022) to enhance functionality and support for sharing and discovering NIH-funded data in generalist repositories. Within the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), the Office of Data Science and Emerging Technologies (ODSET) is responsible for the development and implementation of NIAID's data science strategy. ODSET aims to improve discovery, access, and use of data produced by NIAID-funded research (NIAID, 2022).

There are many methodological constraints when attempting to identify, quantify, and characterize datasets. For example, not all datasets have unique identifiers, datasets may be either "raw" or "aggregated" data, and sometimes datasets are only available upon request. Given these challenges, this effort aims to better understand where and how investigators mention, describe, and/or publish their datasets by assembling a comprehensive list of datasets associated with two specific projects and characterizing these datasets. Additionally, we identify a subset of datasets that can be easily and robustly linked to these projects, as compared to other datasets that could only be discovered via time-intensive manual searching or review of research progress reports. In addition, we hope to better understand how and whether usage or impact of these datasets can be assessed and to inform robust, and at least partially automated, methods to identify and monitor open datasets produced by federally funded research.

Data and methodology

Selection of projects for case study

It is expected that the volume and nature of data produced by research projects will vary depending on the research topic. Additionally, certain data such as survey results or health records are subject to privacy concerns. Data of this nature must be de-identified or aggregated before it can be shared. Different fields may also prefer to share their data in different locations. To get a better view of different scopes of data sharing, NIAID selected two projects from different scientific research areas in order to explore how and whether these different types of data can be identified and assessed using similar methods and whether there is significant variation in where these data can be discovered or how they are reused. An R01 project that generated genomic data and a u19 project that produced clinical data were selected.

Identification of datasets resulting from funded projects

To assemble a list of datasets for each of the two selected projects, we used a variety of approaches leveraging NIH Research Performance Progress Reports (RPPRs), Dimensions grants, publications, and datasets data, and Google search.

RPPRs are written by funded researchers and provided to NIH approximately once per year within the terms of the award and contain updates on project accomplishments and compliance. Relevant RPPR sections include Inclusion Enrollment Reports, Overall Progress Report, Major Activities Sections, and Final Accomplishment Sections. Specific Aims and Research Strategy documents also contain relevant information on planned and used datasets and are more concise than the RPPRs. To identify datasets produced by these projects, we manually reviewed all project RPPRs.

Dimensions is a database of linked information that brings together multiple content types across the research life cycle including awarded grants, publications and their citations, datasets, clinical trials, patents, and policy papers, and aims to provide more complete contextualization of the research (Hook, Porter, & Herzog, 2018). Within Dimensions, datasets are sourced from DataCite which brings together many generalist repositories but is unlikely to include data from domain-specific repositories. Datasets in Dimensions may also be associated with publications which can be linked to funding. Lastly we leveraged Google search to try and identify any straggling datasets not identified by the above methods. Our Google searches typically resulted from mentions of planned or likely-to-have-been-generated datasets mentioned in grant-acknowledging publications and project RPPRs. Since no collection of open datasets is complete and Dimensions does not include datasets from domain-specific repositories, the combined review of grant-acknowledging publications, RPPRs, and manual web searches was necessary to ensure that we obtain a more complete picture of the data produced by these projects.

Our study uncovered 105 datasets across two NIAID-funded projects. The breakdown by number of datasets per project can be seen in Table 1. The majority (58%) of the identified datasets were indexed in Dimensions and identified via automated linkages. The remaining datasets were identified primarily through manual review of grant-acknowledging publications. While RPPRs often mentioned data collection efforts and progress, and would occasionally reference published works, the RPPRs we reviewed did not reference named datasets or dataset identifiers. Similarly, web-based searches did not uncover any additional datasets that could be reliably linked to funding that were not also already discovered through review of grant-acknowledging publications or through automated linkages available in Dimensions.

Characterization of data location and type

Dataset metadata available in Dimensions includes the location (i.e., repository) where the dataset may be found. Manual review was conducted to further group these repositories into four location types: generalist repositories, domain-specific repositories, personal repositories, and online journal repositories. NIH encourages the use of domain-specific repositories such as NCBI GenBank where possible (National Library of Medicine, 2022). However, when a suitable domain-specific repository is not available, generalist repositories may be used. Generalist repositories accept data of all types, formats and from any discipline and are often used by journals to store data associated with published papers. For this project, the subset of generalist repositories that are associated with specific journals have been labeled as “Online Journal Repositories.” Table 1 shows that most datasets identified are located in online journal repositories for both projects, which often include aggregate data from published papers.

Table 1. Number of datasets and data location per project by location type

<i>Project</i>	<i>Number of Datasets (Total)</i>	<i>Location Type</i>	<i>Number and Share of Identified Project Datasets</i>
R01	60	Domain-specific Repository	10 (16.7%)
		Generalist Repository	2 (3.3%)
		Online Journal	47 (78.3%)
		Personal Repository	1 (1.7%)
U19	45	Domain-specific Repository	10 (22.2%)
		Generalist Repository	5 (11.1%)
		Online Journal	30 (66.7%)

Sharing of aggregate data, while useful, has limited utility for other researchers. As such, we wanted to understand how many of the identified datasets included raw data (such as a gene sequence or observation-level records) versus aggregate data. Datasets were labeled as raw or aggregate data through manual review. While the majority of datasets identified from each project were aggregate data, each project also included multiple raw datasets (Table 2).

Table 2. Breakdown of raw versus aggregate datasets per project

<i>Project</i>	<i>Data Type</i>	<i>Number and Share of Identified Project Datasets</i>
R01	Aggregate	49 (81.7%)
	Raw	11 (18.3%)
U19	Aggregate	30 (66.7%)
	Raw	15 (33.3%)

Overall, aggregate data were often provided as supplemental data tables and/or figures describing larger raw datasets. Raw data tended to be gene sequence data submitted to GenBank or a similar repository. Of the 26 raw datasets identified across both projects, 20 datasets are gene sequence data in NCBI Gene Bank or NCBI Sequence Read Archive. Other raw data is varied and includes observation-level survey data, deidentified cohort data, GPS Metadata for transmission tracking and other geospatial data, questionnaire data, and plasmodium genotype data. Raw cohort data were generally not available except in a few instances, either because they were not stored anywhere, or were being withheld to maintain participant confidentiality. We also observed publications featuring data availability statements indicating study authors may be contacted to request data. However, we undertook no outreach to such authors and data availability statements were not analyzed independently during this project.

Assessing feasibility of detection of data reuse/impact

DS identified several potential indications of dataset reuse: Figshare usage statistics, subsequent publications citing NCBI GenBank or Sequence Read Archive accession numbers, and citation metrics for publications associated with datasets (i.e., dataset-originating publications). Figshare is a generalist repository provided at no charge for researchers to provide free public access to data and other research outputs and includes usage statistics for Views and Downloads (Figshare, 2022). Subsequent publications mentioning NCBI accession numbers were identified using Dimensions full-text search. Citation metrics for dataset originating publications were sourced from Dimensions. Of the 105 datasets identified, 68 (64%) are available in Figshare. Almost all of these datasets had at least one view or download (66 out of 68 (97%) and 64 out of 68 (94%) respectively). The distribution of the number of views and downloads is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of Figshare view and downloads (N=68). Dashed lines indicate the average.

Since Figshare usage statistics were not available for NCBI GenBank or Sequence Read Archive datasets, to assess reuse of these datasets we searched for mentions of accession numbers across the full-text of publications in Dimensions. Only a small number of publications (n=2) mentioned the accession numbers from these datasets. However, researchers reusing datasets may be more likely to cite dataset-originating publications than the dataset identifiers themselves. For this reason, citations and altmetrics for dataset-originating publications (n=47) were also explored. Figure 2 shows that dataset-originating publications received an average of almost 16 citations and have an average Altmetric attention score of 15. The Altmetric attention score is an article-level score, indicating the amount of online attention an article has received. Altmetric tracks a unique range of online sources to capture the conversations relating to research outputs. These include public policy documents, mainstream media outlets, blogs, citations, online reference managers, wikipedia, social media, and more (Altmetric, 2021).

Figure 2. Distribution of citations and Altmetric attention scores for dataset originating publications (N=47). Dashed lines indicate the average. The graph has been truncated at 45 for easier visibility. This removed 4 outliers.

Conclusions and next steps

We conducted a deep dive into the datasets produced by two NIAID-funded projects and the feasibility of assessing data reuse and impact. In addition to the datasets easily identified via Dimensions grant linkages, this effort identified many additional datasets and provides a more comprehensive view of datasets linked to these projects. For R01, 60 datasets were identified with 37 out of 60 available in Dimensions. For U19, 45 datasets were identified with 30 out of 45 available in Dimensions. Available datasets consist mostly of aggregate data, such as tables describing larger raw datasets. However, both projects also published raw data. Raw observations were mostly unavailable for U19. Inclusion Data Reports found in the U19 RPPRs clearly and consistently listed out planned data collection and provided status updates (though, for mostly unavailable or untraceable raw data). While beyond the scope of this project, it is

worth noting that this effort also revealed six tools (R packages, models, other software tools) that were explicitly being made available by the tool creators (four from R01 and two from U19). Future efforts may explore more robust methods for capturing the creation of tools, code, and/or software packages in addition to open datasets.

We found that Figshare includes the most robust usage data for the datasets identified in this study. Interestingly, 66 out of the 68 datasets in Figshare had at least one View and 64 out of 68 had at least one Download. While encouraging, these statistics alone cannot tell us how these data were used and whether they led to new or follow-on research projects. Subsequent publications may make use of these data, but it is not clear that researchers regularly cite dataset identifiers in downstream publications. Instead, researchers may be more likely to cite dataset-originating publications. While we observed only two direct references to Accession Numbers in subsequent publications, we found 687 citations to the 47 dataset-originating publications we identified. Future efforts may further characterize citations to the dataset-originating publications to identify the number of citing publications which reuse datasets versus those referring to the major findings from the published papers.

These efforts suggest that it is possible to automate identification of many datasets produced by federally funded grants, but that automated methods will not capture all datasets resulting from federally funded research. Future efforts may conduct a deeper dive into mining the data availability statements from grant-acknowledging publications to extract additional dataset identifiers such as the NCBI accession numbers which are not currently available through automated publication-to-dataset linkages in Dimensions. If the trends observed here hold true for the broader portfolio of NIAID-funded grants, this would mean a significant number of datasets produced by NIAID projects can be identified through automated methods, but that additional identification methods will be necessary to identify all datasets. The degree to which data collection can be automated remains unclear. In addition, regular use and presentation of the metrics on dataset reuse such as Figshare Views and Downloads may help demonstrate the value of open datasets and foster better data stewardship within the research community.

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